

The plasticity of temperature selection and energy demand are uncoupled

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Study question

Does plasticity of behaviour & energy demand play a role in buffering climate variation?

Methods

- Study organism: *Cordylus oelofseni*
- Short-term acclimations (ACC) (ecologically relevant daily temperature fluctuations and photoperiod)
- Summer and Winter: low, average and high ACCs
- Preferred body temperature (T_{sel}): T_b every 10min for 6h in thermal gradient
- Metabolic rate (MR): flow-through respirometry, 3 test temperatures (TT)

E. Schreuder
Cordylus oelofseni

Temperature gradient

Results

T_{sel}

MR

SUMMER

- Plasticity of T_{sel} : lizards acclimated to high ACC select significantly lower mean T_{sel} than the other two acclimation groups (GLZ, ACC effect, $p < 0.05$).
- No plasticity of MR (repeated measures ANOVA; ACC & ACC x TT: $p > 0.05$).

WINTER

- No plasticity of T_{sel} ($p > 0.05$).
- Plasticity of MR: lizards acclimated to high ACC had significantly higher MR than the other two groups (repeated measures ANOVA; ACC effect, $p < 0.05$; ACC x TT, $p > 0.05$).

Conclusions and implications

Cordylus oelofseni buffers short-term climate variations differently in summer and winter. In summer, lizards compensate behaviourally while in winter, energetic adjustments seem to take place. This decoupling has strong implications for incorporating plastic effects into predictive models that forecast ectotherms' responses to climate change.